

THERMAL EXPANSION AND DIMENSIONAL STABILITY OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED ALSI12CUMGNI PISTON ALLOYS

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SUMMARY: Any fluctuation in environmental temperature will introduce internal thermal stresses in metal matrix composites due to the large difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) between the matrix and ceramic reinforcements. These residual stresses have a substantial effect on their dimensional stability and correspondingly, the CTE. This work presents investigations on the evolution of thermal expansion coefficients during thermal cycling for the short-fiber reinforced AlSi12CuMgNi piston alloy. The additions of reinforcements effectively reduce the CTE of the Al-Si alloy. Such reduction in CTE is regarded to be a result of the intense restriction effect of ceramic reinforcement on the KS1275[®] matrix. A large CTE was calculated in the first heating segment. Further thermal cycling leads to a sharp decrease in CTE. The CTE in the longitudinal direction is less than that in the transverse direction due to the different restriction effect. The CTE calculated from the heating segment is larger than that calculated from the cooling segment due to the different internal stress state in the matrix. The CTE evolution is affected by the heat treatment. For the composites investigated, the CTE in the longitudinal direction is more sensitive to the heat treatment than that in the transverse direction, and with increasing aging time the CTE increases.

KEYWORDS: piston alloy, KS1275 alloy, thermal cycling, thermal expansion, internal stress, metal matrix composite

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) offer increased specific strength and stiffness and low thermal expansion coefficient over monolithic materials. Alumina short fiber reinforced Al-12Si alloy composites developed by the Toyota Company or Kolbenschmidt AG for use in diesel engines, are one of the most successful and commercially established applications for metal matrix composites [1-3]. Due to the CTE mismatch between the matrix and reinforcement, any environmental fluctuation in temperature can introduce the internal thermal stress, that can cause the local plastic deformation of the matrix near the reinforcement and introduce plastic strain, leading to an instability in component dimensions during service [4, 5]. As used for precision devices requiring dimensional stability, a higher resistance to micro-deformation is needed. It is important to understand the thermal expansion behavior of such composites and to know any factors that may affect their dimensional stability during service.

Squeeze casting is now the most popular fabrication route for MMCs due to the high productivity of this process and reduced interfacial reactions [5]. However, during squeeze

casting large internal stresses are introduced due to the squeeze pressure and the high solidification rate. These residual stresses have a substantial effect on the dimensional stability and also strongly affect the thermal expansion because these stresses can be released during high temperature applications [1]. Moreover, when the composite is used at high temperatures new thermal stresses are introduced due to temperature fluctuations. These stresses possibly cause the local deformation near the reinforcement, leading to instability in component dimensions and to the degradation of the mechanical properties [6].

CTE is one of the important physical properties of composites that is closely related to the dimensional stability. This paper reports the CTE evolution for short fiber reinforced AlSi12CuMgNi composites during thermal cycling. The thermal cycling experiments approximately simulate the conditions under which the composites experience rapid temperature changes during service. During thermal cycling, new internal stresses can be generated and stress relief can occur. A hysteresis loop is formed between the heating and cooling segment and a residual strain is produced that depends on the heating and cooling rates and also on the properties of the composite constituents [5, 7-11]. Any of these changes are expected to affect the CTE evolution during thermal cycling.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Four composites were selected for the investigation of the thermal expansion behaviors: KS1275[®]+20% Saffil[®] (>95% δ -Al₂O₃, <5% SiO₂), KS1275[®]+20% Maftech[®] (~72% δ -Al₂O₃, ~28% SiO₂), KS1275[®]+20% Kaowool[®] (~47% δ -Al₂O₃, ~53% SiO₂) and KS1275[®]+20% Supertech[®] (~65% SiO₂, ~31%CaO, 4% MgO). The aluminum alloy matrix, KS 1275[®], has a composition (wt.%) of 11~13.5 Si, 0.5~1.3 Cu, 0.8~1.3 Mg, 0.5~1.3 Ni, ~0.25 Zn, ~0.1 Cr, balance Al. The reinforced composites were fabricated by direct squeeze casting. In this process, preforms supplied by Thermal Ceramics de France with a size of 100 mm (diameter) × 20 mm (thickness) were held in a die heated to 200°C. Among the preforms used, both the Saffil[®] and Maftech[®] fibers exhibit a crystal structure, and both the Kaowool[®] and Supertech[®] fibers exhibit an amorphous structure. These preforms contained 20% reinforcement predominately and randomly oriented in the plane of the disc. Molten aluminum alloy was then poured into the die with an applied pressure of 8 MPa.

After squeeze casting, some samples were solution treated at 510°C for 1 hour followed by water quenching and aging at 200°C for various times followed by air cooling. The peak aging time of the KS1275[®] alloy was 225 min and 210 min for the Saffil[®]-fiber reinforced composite [12]. The microstructures of composites were observed on the longitudinal or transverse sections using optical microscopy in the as-polished condition. The unreinforced alloy was etched in a solution of 20 ml distilled water, 100 ml ethanol, 6 ml acetic acid and 12 g picric acid before optical observation. The longitudinal and transverse specimens used for both the CTE measurement and thermal cycling were rectangular with a length of 10 mm and a cross-section area of 5 mm × 5 mm. The investigations of both the CTE and thermal cycling were performed using a quartz tube dilatometer Netzsch Thermische Analyse DIL 402C equipped with TASC 414/3 controller. Both the unreinforced and reinforced samples were cycled 47 times over a temperature range from 58±2 to 287±5°C. Each cycle consists of the heating and

cooling segments with a rate of 10°C/min. For the investigation of CTE comparison among the materials, the CTE was calculated from the first heating segment in a temperature step of 20°C. For the investigation of CTE evolution during thermal cycling, the CTE at the temperature interval 90 to 270°C was calculated from each segment on the thermal cycling curve.

Fig. 1 Optical microstructure, (a) as-cast KS1275[®]+Saffil[®] composite, longitudinal section, without etching, and (b) as-cast KS1275[®] alloy, after etching.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

OPTICAL MICROSTRUCTURE

Fig. 1(a) shows a typical optical microstructure for the as-cast KS1275[®] alloy reinforced with the Saffil[®] fibers. For comparison, the microstructure of the unreinforced alloy is also included (Fig. 1(b)). The fibers remain predominantly in a planar-random arrangement in the composite with relatively few parallel to the disc axis after the infiltration process. The aspect ratio of the short fiber was measured to be about 4.5. There was no significant difference in the optical microstructures among the composites. Whereas the unreinforced alloy shows a pronounced dendritic structure, this is not the case in the composites because free dendritic growth is restricted by the reinforcements. The matrix grains in the composites are smaller than those of the unreinforced alloys.

CTE COMPARISON

Fig. 2(a) shows the CTE as a function of temperature for both the as-cast unreinforced and reinforced alloys. The unreinforced alloy has a higher CTE below 230°C compared to the composites. The composites containing the Saffil[®] and Maftech[®] fibers have a lower CTE than the matrix alloy. For the longitudinal samples, the Supertech[®]-fiber reinforced alloy has the highest CTE. This is also the case when the CTE is measured in the transverse direction when the temperature is below about 200°C. However, above 200°C, the Kaowool[®]-fiber reinforced alloy has a higher CTE than the Supertech[®]-fiber reinforced alloy. The CTEs of the longitudinal samples are lower than that of the transverse samples. The CTE monotonously increases on heating for the transverse samples. This is not the case for the longitudinal samples: the CTE first increases on heating, reaches a maximum and then decreases again. The turning point is sited in the temperature range between 160 to 200°C, which is indicated in Fig. 2(a). Similar phenomenon was also reported by Neite and his coworkers [1]. In their work, the decrease in the

CTE at high temperatures occurred for the longitudinal sample of Saffil[®]-reinforced AlSi12CuMgNi alloy [1]. Fig. 2(b) shows the CTE as a function of the temperature for both the aged unreinforced and reinforced alloys. The overall change in the CTE with the temperature is almost the same as that observed in the as-cast alloys (Fig. 2(a)): as the temperature increases the increase rate of the CTE slows down. However, the CTE tends to be stable, and even decreases for both the transverse and longitudinal samples above 180°C. This is not the case for the as-cast alloys (Fig. 2(a)).

Fig. 2 Coefficient of thermal expansion as a function of temperature for both the unreinforced and reinforced alloys, the CTE was calculated from the first heating segment, (a) as-cast and (b) solution heat treatment followed by peak-aging treatment. TD means the transverse direction and LD means longitudinal direction.

The additions of reinforcements could effectively reduce the CTE of the Al-Si alloy (Fig. 2). Such reduction in the CTE is regarded to be a result of the intense restriction effect of ceramic reinforcement on the KS1275[®] matrix. The decrease in the CTE at high temperatures for the longitudinal samples is due to the fact that these samples have a higher mechanical constraint in contrast to the transverse samples. This fact is also helpful in understanding that the CTE of the longitudinal sample is lower than that of the transverse sample. After aging treatment, fine precipitations are formed in the matrix [12]. These precipitates give an additional restriction on the sample extension, leading to the stable CTE above 180°C in the aged transverse samples. The CTE of composite is also largely related to its initial stress status. The tensile thermal stress generated during squeeze casting could produce an additional thermal expansion, especially at low temperatures. A temperature rise will diminish the internal stress to some extent. This reduction in the internal stress causes the expansion curves of the composites to be steeper at lower temperatures and their slopes lower at high temperatures [1].

CTE EVOLUTION DURING THERMAL CYCLING

Fig. 3 shows the CTE as a function of thermal cycles for both the unreinforced and reinforced alloys. As mentioned above, the CTE of the composite in the longitudinal direction largely decreases due to the addition of the short fibers when compared to the unreinforced alloy. The CTE calculated from the first heating segment is always the highest. After then, it largely decreases and becomes stable. However, the CTE calculated from the cooling segment changes only a little during the whole thermal cycling (Fig. 3(b)). The internal stress generated during

the squeeze casting or during the heat treatment may have a positive effect on increasing the CTE at the first heating stage. After the first thermal cycle, the residual strain that is introduced makes the sample difficult to deform elastically or plastically during the subsequent thermal cycling [12]. The CTE calculated from the heating segments is larger than that calculated from the cooling segments. On cooling, a tensile stress is generated in the matrix that restricts the matrix from contracting. It is therefore expected, that the average CTE in a defined temperature range decreases. After peak aging, the CTE increases. This is thought to be due to the difference in the original thermal residual stresses within these specimens and in their releasing behaviors during the subsequent heating. That the prior thermal processing history has a certain influence on the thermal expansion behavior has also been reported by the other researchers [13]. For both the unreinforced and Maftech[®]-fiber reinforced alloys, their CTEs are stable during the whole thermal cycling. However, the CTE of the Saffil[®]-fiber reinforced alloy largely changes at the early stage of thermal cycling and tends to be stable at the later stage. The different evolution in the CTE could be related to the different material composition. In the Maftech[®]-fiber reinforced alloy, the existence of an interfacial reaction that is caused by the reaction of magnesium with the SiO₂ may improve the interfacial bonding. The improvement of interfacial bonding resulting from the interfacial reaction has been reported by Baxter [14].

Fig. 3 Coefficient of thermal expansion as a function of thermal cycles, (a) calculated from the heating segments and (b) calculated from the cooling segments, at a temperature interval from 90 to 270C°.

Fig. 4 The effect of the heat treatment on the CTE evolution during thermal cycling for the KS1275[®] alloy, (a) CTE was calculated from each heating segment and (b) CTE was calculated from each cooling segment.

Fig. 4 shows the effect of the heat treatment on the CTE evolution during thermal cycling for the unreinforced KS1275[®] alloy. Similar results are observed in Fig. 3:

- the CTE calculated from the first heating segment is always the highest (Fig. 4(a)).
- the CTE calculated from the heating segments is larger than that calculated from the cooling segments. The former is normally in the range of 25 to 27 K⁻¹, while the latter is in the range of 23.5 to 24.5 K⁻¹.

After the first thermal cycling, the CTE increases with increasing aging time. The CTE is a physical property related to the dimensional change. Any elastic or plastic deformation causes a dimensional change will affect the CTE. During thermal cycling, the induced thermal stresses can be larger than the yield stress of the matrix and probably cause the local plastic deformation. As a result, a residual strain after each thermal cycling can be observed. Previous experimental results have shown that this residual strain depends not only on the fabrication process but also on the heat treatment [15]. It is therefore concluded that the thermal expansion behavior should be related to the fabrication process and to the heat treatment history. Kim also reported that the prior thermal processing history has an influence on the thermal expansion behavior [13]. The CTE fluctuation that can be observed in both the Fig. 3 and 4 may be due to the fluctuation in the residual strain. Previous investigations on the residual strain indicated that its evolution during thermal cycling appears fluctuate rather than remain constant [12].

Fig. 5 (a) Thermal cycling curve for the longitudinal sample of the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced alloy solution treated at 510°C for 8 h followed by aging treatment at 200°C for 1h, $d\varepsilon_B$ is the strain change at the bottom temperature and $d\varepsilon_T$ is the strain change at the top temperature. (b) several heating segments, 1st, 5th and 9th are extracted from the Fig. 5(a).

The CTE calculated at the temperature interval from 90 to 270°C is closely related to the slope of thermal cycling curves. Any change in the residual strain at the bottom temperature or in the strain at the top temperature may cause the change in the slope. During thermal cycling, the induced thermal stress has a larger effect on the strain at the bottom temperature. Its effect on the strain at the top temperature is much less due to the stress relaxation at high temperatures. Fig. 5 shows a typical thermal cycling curve for the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced alloy. It can be seen that the strain change at the bottom temperature is much larger than that at the top temperature ($d\varepsilon_B > d\varepsilon_T$). If extracting several heating segments from Fig. 5(a), it is clearly seen that the slope of the curve decreases after the first heating cycle (Fig. 5(b)).

Fig. 6 shows the effect of heat treatment on the CTE evolution for the longitudinal samples of the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced alloy. As observed in the unreinforced alloy, the CTE calculated from the first heating segment has a higher value. The CTE decreases at the early stage of thermal cycling and then becomes stable. For those samples, the heat treatment has an apparent effect on the CTE. The CTE also increases with increasing the aging time. Fig. 7 shows the effect of heat treatment on the CTE evolution for the transverse samples of the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced alloy. For those samples, only the CTE of the as-cast sample obtains a high value from the first heating segment. Unlike the longitudinal samples, the heat treatment has a negligible effect on the CTE. Their CTEs change in a reverse manner with the thermal cycling compared to the longitudinal samples. For both the longitudinal and transverse samples, the CTE calculated from the heating segment is larger than that calculated from the cooling segment.

It is interesting to note that the heat treatment affects the CTEs of the longitudinal and transverse samples in a different way (Fig. 6 and 7). A high dislocation density was always observed near the reinforcement, especially close to the end of short fibers [16]. The high dislocation density is beneficial in increasing the diffusion path of solute atom. The aging

kinetics are apparently accelerated under this situation [17]. It is therefore expected more precipitates could be formed near the ends of short fibers. These precipitates will affect the thermal expansion behavior in the longitudinal direction. However, in the transverse direction their effects are expected to be small. Another possible explanation is the difference in the interfacial bonding strength between the longitudinal and transverse samples that depends on the interfacial reaction. Long heat treatment time at high temperatures could lead to the reaction of the reinforcement with the matrix, leading to the possible change of the bonding strength [18]. The thermal expansion in the transverse direction is less sensitive to changes in the bonding strength than that in the longitudinal direction. Therefore, the CTE in the longitudinal direction is more sensitive to the heat treatment than that in the transverse direction. However, it is still dubious whether the present heat treatments could lead to the different interfacial bonding strength. In the present investigation, the solution treatment is the same for all the samples (longitudinal and transverse samples). However, the subsequent aging treatments are different. During the solution heat treatment an interfacial reaction may occur due to the high temperature [12], but whether this reaction will occur during the aging treatment is unknown because the aging temperature is low (200°C).

Fig. 6 Effect of heat treatment on the CTE evolution during thermal cycling of the longitudinal samples of the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced KS1275[®] alloy, (a) CTE was calculated from each heating segment and (b) CTE was calculated from each cooling segment.

The CTE in the transverse direction has a higher value than in the longitudinal direction as observed in Fig. 2. This difference may also be caused by the different constraints on the matrix from the reinforcement. These constraints have a much larger effect on the local elastic or

plastic deformation in the longitudinal direction. Their effects on the deformation in the transverse direction are small.

Fig. 7 Effect of heat treatment on the CTE evolution during thermal cycling of the transverse samples of the Saffil[®] fiber reinforced KS1275[®] alloy, (a) CTE was calculated from each heating segment and (b) CTE was calculated from each cooling segment.

CONCLUSIONS

The additions of reinforcements could effectively reduce the CTE of the AlSi12CuMgNi piston alloy. Such reduction is regarded to be a result of the intense restriction effect of ceramic reinforcement on the KS1275[®] matrix. The CTE in the longitudinal direction is less than that in the transverse direction due to the different restriction effect. The CTE calculated from the first heating segment has a larger value. The CTE calculated from the heating segment is larger than that calculated from the cooling segment due to the different internal stress state in the matrix. The CTE evolution is affected by the heat treatment. For the composites, the CTE in the longitudinal direction is more sensitive to the heat treatment than that in the transverse direction. With the aging time increasing, the CTE increases.

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